

COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND TECHNOLOGIZATION OF EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The outbreak of COVID-19 and its subsequent declaration as a public health emergency of international concern by the World Health Organisation (WHO) brought about the closure of schools as part of the measures to check and control the spread of the virulent and deleterious disease. This resulted in the abrupt closure of schools, and the adoption of alternative modes of instruction to ensure that teaching and learning did not stop completely during the pandemic. Technologization of education or educational technology was employed by way of electronic or mobile learning, zoom, radio and television broadcasts, and so on. The study adopted the qualitative (non empirical) research method to critically examine the application of technology to education during the COVID-19 pandemic, and its implication for education in post COVID-19 era. The paper observed that technologization of education did not go unencumbered in Nigeria as it was fraught with multifaceted challenges ranging from dearth of infrastructure and technological facilities, lack of requisite and qualified Information Communication Technology personnel, unreliable power supply, lack of quality Internet services and broadcast signals, among others. In view of the enormous benefits inherent in the technologization of education even in the post COVID-19 era, it was recommended that government and private organisations invest resources in the area of educational technology, and that a strong policy in that regard should be formulated with a view of ensuring that it is implemented fully.